

PREPARATION OF CALCIUM PHOSPHATE CEMENT WITH CELLULOSES FIBERS: A SUMMARY.

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ABSTRACT

Calcium phosphate cements (CPC) are well-established materials for the repair of bone defects with excellent biocompatibility and bioactivity. However, brittleness and low flexural/tensile strength restrict their application in orthopaedic surgery to non-load bearing areas. Reinforcement of CPC with fibers can substantially improve its strength and toughness and has been one major strategy to overcome the present mechanical limitations of CPC. We investigated the feasibility of a novel system based on natural cellulosic fibers from different sources -cotton, linen, hemp-. Fibers were successfully included by simple mixing in the cement paste to prepare randomly distributed fiber reinforcement. We characterised the cement paste cohesiveness and injectability. Then we characterised cement compressive and flexural strength. Fiber mass fraction was varied from 1 to 5%. Cement and fibers microstructure, and their interface, were observed by scanning electronic microscopy. We showed that cellulosic fibers bridge cracks in the cement efficiently. Strong variations between fiber types appeared. This system still requires biological evaluation. Celluloses fibers are well integrated by bone but not fully resorbable. Perspectives include chemical treatment of the celluloses to improve its resorbability. This work may increase the interest for natural fiber as a reinforcing material for calcium phosphate cement.

INTRODUCTION

The paper must be written Calcium phosphate cements (CPCs) are an established class of biomaterial for the filling of bone defects in orthopedic surgery, with excellent biocompatibility. They were first described by LeGeros et al. and Brown/Chow in the 1980s [1, 2]. CPCs are integrated in the bone remodeling biological processes, and partially to fully replace with newly formed bone in the range of months. While the biological properties of CPCs are governed by their composition and microstructure, so are their mechanical properties. Commercially available, injectable CPCs show low mechanical strength and low fracture toughness, leading to premature damage of the cement at the implant site [3,4,5], forbidding their use in many indications. CPC's compressive strength can be enhanced by decreasing the material porosity, but at some cost for the biological response. This requires higher Liquid to powder ratio during the cement paste formulation, therefore threatening injectability. [12] This also proved to be inefficient to increase cement fracture toughness.

Pure cements exhibit brittle failure. This is characterized by a small deformation before fracture without any significant non elastic deformation. Therefore the work necessary to induce failure is very low. Brittleness is detrimental to mechanically loaded components and must be compensated for, by greatly increasing the overall dimensions. Their use is typically limited to non-critical applications. Tough and ductile materials are preferred because of their higher tolerance to flaws and impacts. [6] Since case of cement failure can't be compensated by the addition of more cement, in load bearing area, other materials like metal prosthetic hardware or unresorbable polyméthyl metcrylate (PMMA) will be preferred [4].

In the search for a load bearing calcium phosphate cement, no conclusion where reached yet on the ideal scaffold. However, reinforcing the cement with fibers has been a successful strategy to increase the cement fracture toughness. Several reviews [7,19,20,21] report improvement of mechanical properties of fiber reinforced (FR) CPCs. Very different families of fibers were investigated. Many work focus on the potential of not bioresorbable reinforcing material like carbon nanotubes, steel fibers or titanium fibers. Other work focus on improving the biological response with fibers developed from biomaterials like Hydroxapatite whiskers, collagene, fibrin, PLGA. These fibers are biocompatible and degradable, but they have moderate strength. (Xu et al, 2004). Latest work propose very innovative materials like self polymerizing silanized polymers, complex surface treatment of biopolymers, or the use of a magnesium alloy to manufacture resorbable metal fibers [8,9,10,11].

In this study we investigated the potential of a novel system based on a calcium phosphate cement reinforced by a random distribution of natural cellulosic fibers from different sources : cotton, linen and hemp. The interest in natural cellulosic fibers for technical applications recently skyrocketed [13,14]. Cellulose fibers exhibit interesting physical and mechanical properties (low density and well-balanced stiffness, toughness and strength) and are easily available [15]. Vegetable fibers can be found in a wide variety of morphologies – diameter, aspect ratio, length, and surface roughness – and form - strands, pulp or staple -. Moreover, their surface can be easily modified in order to have a more hydrophilic or hydrophobic character or to attach functional groups [16]. Finally, celluloses qualify as a good biomaterial. It is well integrated by bone, does not trigger inflammatory response, and has no toxicity. However, the resorbability of the fibers should be an absolute prerequisite for use in a CPC. Functionalized cellulose is developing and shows better degradation and even improved osteo integration [17,18]. Our objective is to prepare a biomaterial for bone filling indications sensitive to brittleness. The material needs relevant mechanical properties and microstructure.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Preparation of the fibres

The Cotton fibers were purchased from local store. Such fibers are industrially mercerized and sterilized. Cotton fibers were cut to an approximate length of 5mm with scissors. Linen and hemp fibers were provided by the company Fibre Recherche et Développement. The linen and hemp fibers are industrially cut to a maximum length of 5mm and did not undergo any other treatment. Before use, fibers are manually disentangled. Knots and particles are removed.

Fibers length is controlled by direct observation through a x6,3 magnifying lens. Fibers are observed by scanning electronic microscopy (SEM).

Preparation of the fiber reinforced cement

The calcium phosphate cement used in this study is the Graftys Quickset, provided by Graftys. It is an apatitic cement including small amount cellulosic textural polymer. Control cement paste is prepared by manually mixing in a mortar the powder and an aqueous solution of Na₂HPO₄ (0.5% mass), called the hardener, with a liquid/solid ratio of 0,45.

Fiber reinforced calcium phosphate cement (FRCPC) are prepared by simply adding the fibers in the mortar before mixing. We first samples of cement including 1,2 and 5% of cotton, linen and hemp fibers (in powder mass) . After 2 minutes of mixing, part of the paste is used for the assessment of different handling properties and the remaining paste is pushed inside a Teflon mold with a spatula. Two kinds of molds were used: cylindrical mold with 6mm diameter and 12mm height for compression sample and rhombohedral molds of dimensions 36x8x8mm for flexion specimens. An additional thin layer of cement paste is laid with a spatula on every side of the mold were the cement is in contact with the air to protect the sample. After 35 minutes in the air, the mold is placed in a NaCl (0.9% mass) aqueous solution, and then placed in 37°C oven for at least three days. While hardening, the sample is checked for cohesion. Totally non cohesive samples degrade into particles at the bottom of the beaker. After three days, the sample is polished to remove the additional layer and have a clean and smooth surface with a Metaserv 2000 polisher; 800 to 2400 grit/sheet sandpaper. The sample is then demolded and reincubated in the saline solution until it is needed for mechanical testing. All mechanical tests were performed on wet samples.

The setting time is measured by the Gillmore needle test method, as described in previous work [7].

Phase and microstructure characterization

The compositions of hardened CPC specimens by examined by XRD using Cu K_{α} radiation (40 kV, 40 mA) in a continuous scanning mode. The diffraction angle 2θ was varied from 10 to 45° in steps of 0.0167° s⁻¹, with a collection time of 20 s per step. Infrared absorption spectra were recorded by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR; Magna-IR 550, Nicolet Co., USA) in the range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹. Pellets of a 300-mg KBr/1- mg sample were prepared and examined. Finally, the fracture surfaces of CPC specimens were observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM; LEO 1450VP, Carl Zeiss, Germany).

We evaluate global change in the cement porosity by comparison between sample apparent density (m/V) and density of the apatite. Apatite true density chosen value is 2.89 according to previous work. Difference between fiber and cement density was neglected.

Characterization of the mechanical properties

A standard compression test and a standard three-point bending test with a span of 32 mm were used to load the CPC specimens and to measure their compression strength and flexural strength at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/s and 0.2mm/s respectively, up to a displacement of 6 mm on a multifunction mechanical testing machine. Bending specimen were notched by a cut off machine using a diamonded tungsten 0.5 mm saw (Secotom, Struers) in a chevron shape as shown in figure 1. Specimens were kept back in water before testing. After breaking in two, specimen halves were dried and we took pictures of the fractured side. Then the fractured side was observed by electronic microscopy.

Figure 1. Notched bending specimen. **Left:** side view right after bending, a crack is visible coming from the notch and going all the way up. **Right:** front view of the fracture side, after separation of the halves of the bending specimen. Chevron tip is pointing down during bending test.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Fibers characterization

Fiber average length was measured by direct observation through a x6.3 magnifying lens. Fiber diameter was measured by SEM on a small number of fibers. Fiber lengths is 5 ± 3 mm, with a diameter of $10\mu\text{m}$ for cotton and linen and $20\mu\text{m}$ for hemp. Cotton fibers have a very clear toroid shape, as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. Secondary electron micrograph of cotton fibers (left), linen (middle), and hemp (right) scale in red : $10\mu\text{m}$

Fiber reinforced cement characterization

The texture of the paste with fibers is very thick, more difficult to shear than the control. The paste is difficult to separate in several pieces because the fibers are strongly bonded with the paste, cotton gives thicker paste than linen or hemp. After hydration, the paste isn't homogenous until almost the end of the 2 minutes mixing. Cohesion in water was tested immediately after mixing and after 35min

of setting in the air. FRC are cohesive in water. However after 1 day of setting in water at 37°C, outer fibers may have their tip pointing in the water, dragging along small cement particles. All cement hardened well without specific imperfections. FRC also have the same setting time as the control cement.

The IR spectrum and XRD diagrams of control cement and cement reinforced with 2% cotton fibers are displayed in figure 3. We see no impact of the fibers on the hardened cement chemical composition.

The cement reinforced with celluloses fibers generally maintains the good properties of CPCs: composition (fig 3), quick setting, and cohesion in water.

Figure 3. XRD analysis (left) and IR analysis (right) of control and cotton reinforced cement

Microstructure

Apparent density of fiber reinforced cement is identical to that of the control cement at a value of 1.18. SEM observations of the fractured planes of notched specimens are displayed in figure 4. We can see that fibers are randomly distributed and randomly oriented in the cement. Fibers seem to decrease the size of the largest pores. Fibers are significantly pulled out of the cement matrix before breaking. Micro crack are visible on the fracture plane. In the case of FRC, cement pieces are held together by the fibers.

Figure 4: secondary electron micrograph of fractured bending specimen. Left: control cement, right: cement reinforced with cotton fibers. We can see fibers, randomly distributed and significantly pulled out of the cement scale in red : 100 μm

Mechanical properties

Cement reinforced with celluloses fiber does not have an increase compressive strength. However, while control cement pieces scatter after first crack reinforced cement holds together and displays a significant resistance during following deformation. By bridging the cracks, fibers maintain up to 60% of cement compressive strength after the matrix breakup.

Reinforced cement also exhibit increased bending strength, with a strong correlation with fiber mass fraction (figure 5). Fiber reinforcement strength is determined by several mechanisms: fiber deformation (elastic and then non elastic until failure of the fiber), crack deflection, and frictional sliding (the energy spend to pull out the fiber from the cement) [19,34]. The leading mechanism will be the one of lower energy, and the best reinforcement will be achieved especially if pull-out strength of the fiber is close to their tensile strength [27]. This is highly dependent on the interfacial interaction between the cement and the fibers. Figure 4 shows that cellulosic fibers are significantly pulled out of the cement matrix before breaking. This pull out indicates there is way for improvement of the fiber reinforcement.

Figure 5: typical force/displacement curves of bending test with a fiber reinforced cement.

CONCLUSIONS

We succeeded in formulating of calcium phosphate cement including a random distribution of natural cellulosic fibers from different sources. This material is very easy to prepare and to use. Natural fibers showed interesting performances for CPC reinforcement. Pure cellulose is not an optimal biomaterial but the mechanical properties of our system may increase the interest in celluloses fiber reinforced CPC, provided that cellulose chemical modification increases its biodegradability.

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